

Grating Integration Technologies for Edge Emitting AlGaAs Diode Lasers

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Motivation

- Gratings integrated in AlGaAs laser diodes for
 - Defined wavelengths
 - Narrow linewidths: ridge waveguide DFB < 10 MHz; DBR < 200 kHz
 - Reduced thermal shift with current induced thermal heating
- Laser sources in optical systems for various applications, e.g.
 - Sensing (LIDAR, OCT)
 - Imaging (digital holography)
 - Spectroscopy (Raman)
 - Metrology (optical clocks)

Overgrown Gratings

- 1st MOVPE ends with InGaP/GaAs(P) grating layers (high etch selectivity)
- Lithography (typ. Vistec SB251); wet chemical and CBr₄ in-situ etching
- 2nd epitaxy to complete the vertical structure

- OG with GaAsP grating lines and InGaP protection layer embedded in AlGaAs (periode to grating line (PTG) 240 nm/ 100 nm)

- OG with InGaP grating lines embedded in GaAs (PTG of 140 nm/ 70 nm)

Examples

- DFB laser for atomic clocks (potassium D2 line)

- Schematic, LI-curve and spectral mapping of 767nm DFB laser ($\kappa < 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

- Sampled grating DBR laser for wide akinetic λ tuning (down conversion)

- Schematic and spectra for different tuning currents of a 970nm DBR laser ($\kappa > 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

Comparison and Summary

Grating integration technology	Control of coupling strengths κ	Grating order m	Pros	Cons
Surface etched grooves (SE)	Depths and shape of etched grooves	> 2	Single epitaxial step	Control of etch depth
Epitaxial overgrowth (OG)	Epitaxial layer thicknesses and duty cycle	1 or 2	Dimensions defined by epilayers	Oxygen incorporation, growth depends on crystal orientation

- The choice of the best fabrication processes is influenced by the vertical epitaxial structure for the laser and the available equipment.
- Both grating integration technologies are applied to standard fabrication processes at FBH to produce medium quantities of various types of DBR and DFB lasers (see examples).

Grating Integration Challenges

- High brilliance/power lasers require the integration of gratings
 - With defined coupling coefficient κ
 - Without degrading the Electro-Optical (OE) efficiency
- Overgrown gratings (OG)
 - AlGaAs is prone to oxygen which increases leakage currents
 - High propagation velocity of crystal defects
- Surface etched gratings (SE)
 - κ depends critical on depths/shape of the grating grooves

Surface Etched Gratings

- Ti/nLOF (50nm/ 800nm) hardmask structured with RIE (SF₆/O)
- In-situ control of the etching process
- Up to 1500nm deep grooves into AlGaAs RIE (BCl₃; Ar) with a precision of $\pm 50 \text{ nm}$

- SG with 1.3 μm deep V-shaped grooves (PTG at the top 420 nm/ 150 nm and at the bottom 20 nm/ 30 nm)

- DBR array for digital holography (3D scanners)

- DBR array with 24 individually controllable emitters (pitch 45 μm) optical spectra with 0.5 nm spacing ($\kappa > 60 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

- SE are also applied for λ stabilised 905nm high power pulse sources (> 40W; 2-10ns) with broad area laser diodes (LIDAR)